

Chemisorption Kinetic Studies of Oxygen on V_2O_5 - Ti_2O_3

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From studies on the chemisorption of oxygen over V_2O_5 - Ti_2O_3 mixture and V_2O_5 separately, it was observed that the mixture exhibited higher activity. With the help of X-ray, DTA and magnetic measurement of the sample an attempt has been made to correlate the enhanced activity with the changed oxidation states. Elovich equation was found to be obeyed in all cases. Attempt has also been made to represent the probable mechanisms of the reaction.

VANADIUM pentoxide is known as an important catalyst for oxidation reactions. Different investigations on the various aspects of V_2O_5 like X-ray structure analysis, adsorption studies, thermal behaviour, catalytic activity etc. has established that the anomalous behaviour of V_2O_5 is due probably to the peculiar geometry^{1,2,3} as well as different composition of the oxide. The presence of lower valent states, either singly or in combination with V_2O_5 , is responsible for catalytic reaction (oxidation)⁴. However, the existence of lower valent states and the presence of different phases with varying composition make it difficult to attribute the catalytic activity uniquely to any particular oxidation state.

Titanium sesquioxide, Ti_2O_3 , isomorphous with V_2O_5 and Cr_2O_3 shows anomalous electrical and magnetic properties related in origin to V_2O_5 . It has been observed from a study of the states of TiO_2 heated in vacuum⁵ that at 300° it is partially reduced to Ti^{3+} while on heating to 500° and above not only oxygen but also titanium enter gas phase and a compound, $Ti_{1-x}O_{2-y}$, where $y > x$ is formed. This process can lead, on subsequent treatment of the TiO_2 with oxygen, to the development of p-type semiconductivity, though V_2O_5 normally exhibits n-type semi-conductivity. It is assumed that the change in the properties of TiO_2 , when treated under various conditions, is caused by a shift of the reaction $Ti^{3+} + O_2 = Ti^{4+}/O_2$. Thus, Ti^{3+} [defects]

Fig. 1. Plot of Δp vs $\log(t+k)$.

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Fig. 2. Adsorption isotherms (a) and isobars (b)

Adsorption isotherms (a)

 325°—△...△—
 300°—○...○—
 375°—●...●—
 350°—□...□—
 275°—⊗...⊗—

 Adsorption isobars (b)
 Pressures

 2 cm —○...○—
 2.5 cm —△...△—
 3.0 cm —□...□—
 3.5 cm —●...●—
 4.0 cm —⊗...⊗—

appearing on TiO_2 lattice must always be accompanied by the evolution of molecular oxygen which has been found to be true only at temperature of 500° and above.

ation. But heating the catalyst in vacuum would again lead to partial reduction and Ti^{3+} formation as in TiO_2 . So, V_2O_5 containing Ti_2O_3 as prepared would act as if it is a mixture of $V_2O_5-TiO_2$. We, thus, aimed to study the effect of incorporation on chemisorption and electrical conductivity studies of V_2O_5 with Ti_2O_3 .

Preparation of sample : The sample of V_2O_5 was prepared as described earlier⁶. The sample of titanium sesquioxide used was prepared⁷ by the reduction of TiO_2 by passing pure, dry hydrogen with titanium tetrachloride at 750° for 48 hr.

The sample of vanadium pentoxide containing titanium sesquioxide, $V_2O_5-Ti_2O_3$, was prepared by mixing V_2O_5 and Ti_2O_3 in 3 : 1 mole ratio respectively in a porcelain basin at 800°-1000° in nitrogen atmosphere. The resulting product, after cooling, was extracted with oxalic acid, evaporated and decomposed in vacuum. The particle size chosen was -120+140 B.S.S.

Characterisation of the sample : The sample of V_2O_5 was analysed chemically by the method of Caderbank⁸ and the sample of Ti_2O_3 was analysed by both volumetric⁹ and gravimetric methods. 1.1% of V^{4+} ions were present in the sample of V_2O_5 . In the volumetric analysis of Ti_2O_3 , calculation on the basis of the equation $V^{5+}+Ti^{3+} \rightarrow V^{4+}+Ti^{4+}$ gave the % of Ti^{3+} in the prepared Ti_2O_3 as 66%. A direct method for gravimetric analysis of the

TABLE 1—MODEL RESULTS OF ADSORPTION OF OXYGEN

Expt. No. 7 $P_0 = 17.05$ cm of Hg. $T = 300^\circ$		Expt. No. 10 $P_0 = 27.2$ cm of Hg. $T = 300^\circ$		Expt. No. 8 $P_0 = 8.8$ cm of Hg. $T = 350^\circ$	
Time (min)	Δp (cm of Hg)	Time (min)	Δp (cm of Hg)	Time (min)	Δp (cm of Hg)
1	0.07	1	0.10	1	0.08
2	0.08	2	0.12	2	0.10
3	0.10	4	0.15	3	0.12
5	0.12	6	0.17	5	0.14
7	0.13	8	0.19	7	0.16
9	0.14	10	0.21	9	0.18
11	0.16	12	0.23	11	0.20
13	0.17	15	0.24	15	0.22
15	0.20	20	0.25	20	0.24
20	0.20	25	0.26	25	0.25
25	0.23	30	0.27	30	0.27
30	0.23	40	0.28	40	0.30
40	0.25	50	0.29	50	0.32
		60	0.32		

For the present investigation we have used the catalyst V_2O_5 containing Ti_2O_3 in 3 : 1 mole ratio prepared at high temperature. It is certain that Ti^{3+} in the mixture is converted to Ti^{4+} during its prepar-

Fig. 3. DTA thermograms. Heating curve— — — — — Cooling curve— - - - -

TABLE 2—MODIFIED ELOVICH PARAMETERS

Expt. No.	Temp.	Pressures (cm of Hg)	α (cm ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	k (min)	t ₀ (min)	a*(a) (cm g min ⁻¹)	Δp_0 (cm)
7	300	17.05	9.979	7	3.860	0.01451	0.0597
15	325	17.05	7.757	7	1.063	0.01842	0.2431
11	350	17.05	7.119	7	58.880	0.02007	-0.2991
24	375	17.05	7.037	7	1.484	0.02031	0.1051
10	300	27.20	15.35	1	0.4861	0.06515	0.047
18	325	27.20	16.89	7	0.003303	0.008460	0.4534
20	350	27.20	15.35	1	0.05413	0.06515	0.195
25	375	27.20	8.011	7	-1.1719	0.01783	0.2167
8	350	8.80	8.80	7	3.394	0.01621	0.0818
22	375	8.80	9.234	7	1.452	0.01547	0.1663
21	350	13.00	21.18	7	0.03442	0.006743	0.2506
23	375	13.00	6.50	7	-1.4084	0.021984	0.2721

TABLE 3—VALUES OF $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$, CALCULATED FROM Δp VS LOG t PLOTS

Expt No.	Temp (°C)	Pressure (cm of Hg)	α (cm ⁻¹ gm)		α_3
			α_1	α_2	
7	300	17.05	40.64	12.62	—
15	325	17.05	26.90	10.40	—
11	350	17.05	33.91	10.80	—
24	375	17.05	40.68	9.003	—
10	300	27.20	21.08	—	—
18	325	27.20	49.73	—	—
20	350	27.20	30.11	7.754	—
25	375	27.20	30.11	15.25	—
8	350	8.80	24.73	11.74	—
22	375	8.80	21.08	5.27	—
21	350	13.00	31.62	—	—
23	375	13.00	24.84	9.003	6.39

sample, $Ti_2O_3 + \frac{1}{2}O_2 \rightarrow TiO_2$ was done and the value obtained was 99% of the theoretical value.

It is known that V^{5+} is a strong oxidising agent and Ti^{3+} a very strong reducing agent. In the oxide obtained by heating a mixture of V_2O_5 and Ti_2O_3 it is almost certain that Ti^{3+} has been completely oxidized to Ti^{4+} and simultaneously V^{5+} has been reduced to some other lower valent states. Thus no chemical analysis of the sample regarding the oxidation states of the vanadium in it was attempted.

X-ray powder photograph of the specimen was obtained using a 2865 mm dia camera (Philips model PW 1008) and chromium radiation ($\lambda=2.291 \text{ \AA}$) in

Fig. 4. (a) Plot of $\log (\text{rate}) \left[\text{Log} \left(\frac{d\Delta P}{dt} \right) \right]$ vs $1/T \times 10^3$.

(b) Plot of activation energy (E) vs coverage (ΔP).

ΔP (.1) — $\circ \dots \circ$
 ΔP (.2) — $\triangle \dots \triangle$
 ΔP (.3) — $\square \dots \square$
 ΔP (.4) — $\circ \dots \circ$

Fig. 5. Plot of $\text{Log } a^*$ vs $1/T \times 10^3$.

Expt. 55-60 — $\triangle \dots \triangle$
 Expt. 46-51 — $\circ \dots \circ$
 Expt. 70-74 — $\square \dots \square$

the absence of any filter. Approximately 6 hr exposure was given at 25KV and 10 MA. Results are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—X-RAY ANALYSIS DATA

Sample (After preparation)		Sample (after O ₂ kinetics)	
Intensity	d(Å)	Intensity	d(Å)
F (B)		VF (B)	1.383
M	1.685	F (D)	1.738
VF	2.242	VF	1.840
VF	2.479	F	2.269
F	3.152	VF	2.583
		F	3.00
		M	3.388
		M	3.534
		F	4.557
		VF	5.920

Magnetic susceptibility was determined by using a Guoy balance at a field strength of 3.64×10^5 gauss. Standard DTA analysis was done using

Fig. 6. Plot of χ vs $1/T$.
17 cm (pressure) —○...○
27.2 cm (pressure) —○...○

γ -alumina as the reference. Surface area measurement was done by conventional BET method using liquid nitrogen and the surface area before and after adsorption were found to be $14.1 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and $20.2 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ respectively. Oxygen gas used was prepared following the procedure described earlier⁶.

Experimental

The method for sample preparation and degassing and the form of the Elovich equation^{10,11} applied has been described by De and Gadgil⁶. The kinetic measurements were carried out in the temperature range $275^\circ\text{--}375^\circ$ using oxygen.

Adsorption isotherms were obtained and isosteric heats of adsorption were calculated from the isotherms by the use of Clausius-Clapeyron equations :

$$\log (P_1/P_2)_\theta = \frac{\Delta H_\theta}{4.57} \left(\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1} \right) \quad \dots (1)$$

where the terms have their usual significance. Isobars have also been plotted.

At temperatures 300° and 325° kinetics proceeds too slowly within the pressure range 4.7-13 cm of Hg. So kinetics was studied at pressures 17.02 and 27.2 cm of Hg. All other measurements were done between 4.7-27.2 cm of Hg.

Results and Discussion

Chemisorption of oxygen does not proceed at low temperatures and pressures over this sample. Adsorption starts at 300° for an initial pressure of 17 cm and 27.2 cm of Hg, and for 350° and 375° at other lower initial pressures ; e. g., $P_0=13$ cm and 8 cm of Hg.

All the plots of Δp vs $\log t$ are linear with discontinuities with one or two breaks. But by choosing a suitable value of 'k' they could be linearised with the exception of two expts. The plots of α vs $1/T$ do not show any regular variation with $P_0=17$ cm. α vs $1/T$ plot is parabolic whereas with $P_0=27.2$ cm the plot shows a maximum at 325° . So a change in the nature of active sites¹² occur at 325° , at least for $P_0=27.2$ cm of Hg. Adsorption isotherm studies indicate the adsorption to be highest at 325° and was further supported by an endothermic peak in the DTA thermogram at 325° proving this to be a characteristic temperature of the catalyst in respect of its behaviour as an oxidation catalyst (for oxygen chemisorption).

The initial massive adsorption, a^* , increases with temperature for $P_0=17$ cm, but for $P_0=27.2$ cm at 375° there is some deviation in the trend of increase shown in the plot of $\log a^*$ vs $1/T$. Activation energy was calculated using a^* (a_1) with the help of the equation :

$$\log (\text{rate}) = \log \left(\frac{d \Delta p}{dt} \right) = \log a - \frac{\alpha}{2.303} \times \Delta P_0 \quad \dots (2)$$

It has been found to be 4.37 K cal/mole for $P_0=17$ cm and 9.14 K cal/mole for $P_0=27$ cm. Plot of

TABLE 5—ISOSTERIC HEAT OF ADSORPTION (ΔH) CALCULATED FROM THE ISOTHERMS

300°–350°		300°–375°		325°–350°		325°–375°		350°–375°	
V(cc)	(K. Cal) ΔH								
3.0	2.48	3.0	17.80	3.0	15.96	3.0	33.8	3.0	53.08
3.5	3.46	3.5	17.60	3.5	15.75	3.5	31.99	3.5	49.55
4.0	3.80	4.0	16.36	4.0	14.90	4.0	29.10	4.0	44.38
4.5	3.13	4.5	15.40	4.5	14.19	4.5	27.90	4.5	42.73
5.0	3.07	5.0	15.44	5.0	14.70	5.0	28.47	5.0	43.36
5.5	3.07	5.5	14.89	5.5	15.67	5.5	28.06	5.5	41.02
6.0	2.58	6.0	14.09	6.0	17.87	6.0	28.56	6.0	40.11

activation energy (E) vs coverage (Δ_p) is not linear, but shows a maximum around $\Delta_p = 0.03$ cm. The parameter ' t_0 ' which according to Low¹³ indicates the time at which slow adsorption starts, has been found to be irregular in the present case and is probably of minor importance.

It is rather certain that during the preparation of the sample $V_2O_5-Ti_2O_3$, Ti^{3+} present would have been oxidized to Ti^{4+} with simultaneous conversion of V^{5+} to V^{4+} and possibly to other lower valent states. But from the study of the states of TiO_2 heated in vacuum⁶, it has been shown that it is converted to an non-stoichiometric compound of the type $Ti_{1-x}O_{2-y}$ (titanium and oxygen entering gas phase) and Ti^{3+} is formed. X-ray analysis data show two strong lines with those of TiO_2 (Ti^{4+}) supporting our view.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements give μ_{eff} to be 3.67 B.M. as against 3.89 indicating the presence of 3 unpaired electrons.

After pretreatment and evacuation of catalyst, probable sites for attach may be Ti^{3+} , V^{4+} , V^{5+} and other lower valent states of vanadium. Oxygen may be adsorbed on these sites either as O^- , O_2^- or O^- species. But at high temperatures, the formation of the species O_2^- ¹⁴ is ruled out owing to the fact that physically adsorbed oxygen may be a weakly chemisorbed species like O_2^- ¹⁴. From the table of heat of adsorption for the temperature range 350°–375°, ΔH varies from 53–40 K cal. It is highly probable that at this temperature oxygen will be adsorbed as O^- , forming higher oxides. It has also been observed that after the chemisorption of oxygen, the chemisorption of hydrogen on the same specimen is higher indicating the likely adsorption of O^- species.

From the X-ray spectroscopic data of the sample after oxygen chemisorption studies, a very strong line has been found to coincide with a very strong line of TiO_2 (Rutile) indicating the formation of the higher oxide. The probable mode of adsorption may be:

The conductivity of the pelleted sample was measured both in vacuum and in oxygen atmosphere. The conductivity in oxygen atmosphere at 300° increased in the first minute from 27.02×10^{-4} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ to 78.15×10^{-4} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and then decreased continuously. The reason for this increase is probably the adsorption of O^- species, because O^- species have a tendency to donate one electron to the conduction band forming uncharged ' O ' species. This has also been proved by the work of Morrison¹⁵. Adsorption in the later stage may proceed as

leading to a decrease in the conductance. The O^- species may accept an electron from the F centre or from the conduction band to form O^- species. This O^- may fill up the lattice vacancies leading to the formation of TiO_2 and higher oxides of vanadium. As has been stated, the adsorption of oxygen directly as O^- is also not unlikely. But whatever may be the case, it is almost certain that excess of O^- are created after oxygen adsorption.

Conclusion :

From previous work⁴ the activity of V_2O_5 has been attributed to the joint presence of V_2O_5 and $V_2O_{4.54}$ involving a dynamic equilibrium between V_2O_5 like structure and $V_2O_{4.54}$ like structure. Some recent work on the oxidation involving V_2O_5 ¹⁶ suggest that the presence of different lower valent states are responsible for catalytic reactions. We have deliberately added Ti_2O_3 , introducing more of defect centres and our work seem to corroborate this view. From the work of Bhattacharyya *et al*¹⁷ and our work⁶, the adsorption does not proceed at low temperatures, pressures and small amounts of sample. Comparison of the results show that the defects introduced play a definite role in the adsorption of oxygen facilitating oxidation reactions.

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